

CORES_{TO} CODE

Science Handbook

CPAL

Cascadia Paleoseismology Working Group

CRESCENT
CASCADIA REGION EARTHQUAKE
SCIENCE CENTER

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Acknowledgment of Contributors

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Cascadia Subduction Zone

The Cascadia subduction zone (CSZ)

The CSZ is a ~1,300 km long convergent boundary, extending from northern California to Vancouver Island, produced by the subduction of the Juan de Fuca plate beneath the North American plate. Map to the left shows locations, on and offshore, where geologic evidence of past CSZ earthquakes are preserved.

HYPOTHESES: ALL AT ONCE OR A PIECE AT A TIME?

Giant earthquake, M 9

Series of lesser events, M 8+

Rupture scenarios

Outstanding questions exist about how the CSZ ruptures during great earthquakes. A) the full-length rupture hypothesis B) the “serial rupture” hypothesis.

Key Terms

Great earthquake:

Term used to describe powerful subduction zone earthquakes of magnitude greater than magnitude 8.0

Subduction:

The downward movement of a geologic plate beneath another plate

Juan de Fuca plate:

Oceanic tectonic plate of the earth’s crust

North American plate:

Continental tectonic plate of the earth’s crust

Onshore:

Locations at or near the shore (e.g., tidal marshes, coastal lakes)

Offshore:

Locations distal from the shore (e.g., underwater deposition systems)

Rupture:

Extent of slip that takes place along a fault during an earthquake

Rupture scenario:

A potential explanation of how past earthquakes behaved based on geologic evidence

Paleoseismology:

The study of past earthquakes to understand their location, timing and size

Subduction Zone Earthquake Deformation Cycle

Interseismic

Interseismic period

- Gradual, slow, deformation over hundreds of years
- Overriding plate and subducting plate are “stuck” together
- Overriding plate deforms from this stress as it is squeezed
- The front edge of the plate (offshore) is dragged downward while inland portions of the plate bulges upward (along the coast)
- This vertical deformation along the coastline produces a relative sea-level (RSL) change
- As the land moves up, the RSL at the site goes down, producing RSL fall

Coseismic

Coseismic period

- This is the time of when the earthquake happens
- Sudden deformation over seconds to minutes
- Where the plates were “stuck” together, they become “unstuck” and freely slip
- Stress that had been building up during the **interseismic period** is suddenly released
- The front edge of the plate (offshore) is rapidly uplifted, deforming the water column and possibly producing a tsunami
- Along the coastline there is vertical deformation as the land “drops” producing subsidence
- As the land subsides, the RSL at the site goes up, producing RSL rise

Key Terms

- Overriding plate:** Tectonic plate that is positioned above a subduction plate
- Subducting plate:** Tectonic plate that is passing below another tectonic plate
- Relative sea-level:** The height of the ocean surface at a specific location, relative to the land at that location
- Slip:** The amount and direction of movement along a fault during an earthquake

Subduction Zone Earthquake Stratigraphy

How is earthquake evidence preserved in tidal wetland stratigraphy?

Tidal wetlands preserve evidence of subduction zone earthquakes through abrupt shifts in background sedimentation. Changes in land-level and relative sea-level (RSL), caused by coseismic subsidence and interseismic uplift, produce distinct lithologic transitions. These sequences record the geologic evidence associated with past subduction zone earthquake deformation cycles.

1. Before the earthquake, coastal land lies above the mean tidal level (MTL) and is represented by a high marsh. During this period, sedimentation is dominated by organic material, forming **peat** composed of rooted herbaceous plant matter.
2. During a subduction zone earthquake, near-instantaneous vertical land deformation causes coastal subsidence, lowering the land within the tidal frame and resulting in a relative sea level (RSL) rise.
3. If the earthquake generates a tsunami, the incoming wave can transport sand from the beach or inlet onto the marsh surface. Tsunami deposits are typically composed of clastic sediments, ranging in grain size from very fine to medium sand.
4. The subsided land now lies below the MTL, causing a shift in sedimentation from organic marsh material to marine-derived silt and clay, often referred to as **tidal mud** or simply **mud**.
5. Over the following decades to hundreds of years, the interseismic period gradually uplifts the land again, preserving these lithologic changes within the stratigraphic record.
6. Photograph: Sediment core showing earthquake stratigraphy preserved in a tidal marsh. At the base is a pre-earthquake organic peat, overlain by a tsunami-deposited sand unit, and capped by silty mud.

Troels-Smith Classification System

The **Troels-Smith classification system** is a descriptive method for characterizing and documenting the composition of unconsolidated sediments, particularly useful in **wetland stratigraphy**.

Key features of the Troels-Smith system:

- Describes sediments in terms of composition, structure, and consistency.
- Uses **letter codes** for different material components and **numerical codes** to indicate their relative abundance.
- Each material component listed as a proportion of a total of 4 parts (1 = ~25%, 2 = ~50%, 3 = ~75%, 4 = ~100%)
- Example: Th2 Sh1 Ag1 = ~50% rooted peat, ~25% decomposed organics, ~25% silty mud

Material component	Code	Latin base name	Description of material component
Rooted organics	Tl ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Turfa lignosa</i>	Rooted woody peat - stumps, roots, rootlets, branches, trunks, stems, of woody plants
	Th ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Turfa herbacea</i>	Rooted herbaceous peat - roots, rootlets, rhizomes, stems, leaves of herbaceous plants
Detrital organics	Dl ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Detritus lignosus</i>	Unrooted fragments of woody plants >2 mm
	Dh ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Detritus herbosus</i>	Unrooted fragments of herbaceous plants >2 mm
Mud	As ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Argilla steadotes</i>	Particles of clay <0.002 mm
	Ag ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Argilla granosa</i>	Particles of silt 0.002–0.06 mm
Sand	Ga ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Grana arenosa</i>	Particles of sand 0.06–2 mm; (Fine (f) 0.06–0.2, medium (m) 0.2–0.6, coarse (co) 0.6–2.0 mm)
Decomposed organics	Sh ⁰⁻⁴	<i>Substantia humosa</i>	Humous substance, highly decomposed, homogeneous microscopic structure

Other critical components of sediment descriptions: color, word description, and contact

Color: describe the color of the observed unit (e.g., red brown or blue grey)

Word description: describe the Troels-Smith in common verbiage

Contact: How rapid is the change from one unit to the next? Contacts are described in millimeters (mm) and describes how quickly one unit changes to the next: abrupt (>1 – 1 mm), sharp (1– 5 mm), clear (5 – 10 mm), and gradual (>10 mm).

A complete sediment description includes: [Troels-Smith](#), [color](#), [word description](#), and [contact](#)

Examples: Th2 Sh1 Ag1, red brown rooted silty peat, contact over 3 mm
Ag3 Ga1, blue grey sandy silt, contact over 10 mm

Describing Sediment Cores

SR23.OPB2

Overview

A core description characterizes a sediment core by identifying and interpreting distinct lithologic layers. These descriptions start by recording the core's depth and orientation, then divide it into layers based on grain size, organic content, texture, and color—whether it's dark-brown, rooted mud; light-grey, sand; or mixed grain sizes. Look for earthquake indicators like sharp contacts where sand abruptly overlies peat, normal-graded sand deposits, or disturbed bedding. Photograph the entire core and each section marking any major changes in grain size, color bands, or plant fragments. Together, these observations create a detailed “log” that links core layers to past subduction earthquakes, helping you interpret when and how strong those events were.

Materials needed:

- Measuring tape
- Notebook or excel document
- Knife
- Camera (phone)
- Paper towels

Steps:

1. Line a up a tape measure to the top and bottom depths of the sediment core. Make sure you are aware of which side is top and which is bottom.
2. Using a knife, carefully clean the surface of the core to remove contaminating and oxidized material so that stratigraphic contacts are clearly visible. To do so, gently scrape off a thin layer of sediment moving across the width of the core. Wipe the blade periodically to avoid cross-contamination of sediment layers.
3. Take a photo of the full length of the core, making sure the adjacent tape measure is visible and readable.
4. Begin to mark major contact distinctions to start describing - these can change once you start describing
5. Using the Troels-Smith classification system start describing the top stratigraphic layer. Focus on grain size, organic content (roots, plant detritus, decomposed organics), and color. Be sure to recorded the start and end depths for the layer.
6. Describe the transition to the following layer. Is it abrupt (e.q. 2mm) or gradual (e.q. 15mm)?
7. Write a written description of the layer. (e.q. Medium-grey, medium to very fine sand; Dark-brown, decomposed rooted peat)

Subsampling Sediment Cores

SR23.OPB2

Overview

Subsampling a sediment core is the first step in any laboratory investigation of past environmental or seismic events, and it sets the stage for every analysis that follows. During this phase, small, precisely measured intervals of the core are removed at predetermined intervals using clean, dedicated tools to ensure that each subsample represents a discrete moment in the core's history and avoid cross-contamination. Careful subsampling preserves a core's vertical stratigraphy and yields data that more accurately represents the sampled core.

Materials needed:

- Measuring tape
- Notebook or sampling document
- Knife
- Beaker or Falcone tube
- Paper towels
- Sharpie
- Mass scale (g)
- Camera (phone)

Steps:

1. Line up a tape measure to the top and bottom depths of the sediment core. The top and bottom depths can be found on the cores label. Make sure you are aware of which side is top and which is bottom.
2. Using a knife, carefully clean the surface of the core to remove contaminating and oxidized material so that stratigraphic contacts are clearly visible. To do so, gently scrape off a thin layer of sediment moving across the width of the core. Wipe the blade periodically to avoid cross-contamination of sediment layers.
3. Take a photo of the full length of the core, making sure the adjacent tape measure is visible and readable.
4. Plan out the 1 cm intervals you will subsample. It is standard to sample 5 cm below the subsidence contact and 10 cm above the subsidence contact (or 5 cm above the inferred tsunami deposit). Keep in mind the depth of the subsidence contact, as this may not be a whole number, and can affect the starting interval.
5. Label the beakers (or falcon tubes) that will hold your samples. The label should contain the full core ID and depth interval.
6. Sample a cubic centimeter from a chosen interval and place it in the appropriate beaker.
7. Weigh the sample on a mass scale. Try to target approximately 1g. Make sure to zero the scale to the empty beaker first.
8. Record the mass in a notebook or sampling document.
9. Repeat steps 6-8 for each interval.

Loss on Ignition (LOI) Procedure

What do you need?

- Scale
- Oven that can get up to 500°C for organic matter (up to 1000°C for inorganic C)
- Crucible
- Sediment samples

1. Place desired sample volume into pre-weighed crucible (1-3g is plenty).
2. Re-weigh the crucible with the sample. Record the weight as the wet mass.
3. Dry the sample for 24 hours at 100°C in an oven.
4. Re-weigh the crucible with the sample. Record the weight as the dry mass.
5. This value divided by your volume is your dry bulk density (mass/volume; typically, g/cm³)
6. Place the crucibles into a 550°C furnace for one hour.
7. Remove crucible from furnace (once safe), let cool to room temperature in a desiccator prior to re-weighing.
8. Re-weigh crucibles with combusted sample.
9. Your % organic matter will then be: (original weight of sample – combusted sample weight)/original sample weight

*remember to subtract the crucible weight from the total weights to get your sample weights!

** If you want you can then do basically the same procedure with your combusted sample at 1000°C to estimate the amount of inorganic carbon content.

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Agglutinated Foraminifera

What are Foraminifera?

Foraminifera (forams for short) are a type of single celled protist that have been abundant in the fossil record for the last 540 million years. Agglutinated foraminifera have tests (shells) made of cemented organic matter and sand and silt particles.

Why do we study forams?

Studying forams has many applications such as biostratigraphy and paleoecology. More specifically, species of forams are particular about where they live. Even within estuaries and marshes, different species of forams are only abundant in certain areas of the marsh (tidal flat, low, middle, high, upland). By studying and comparing the assemblages of forams within sediment cores, we can gain an understanding of the previous environment that used to exist at the core location, for example the type of marsh environment that was present before and after an earthquake and associated subsidence.

Foraminifera Anatomy

Where do they live?

Forams live in every marine habitat within our world's oceans spanning the open ocean to brackish waters. Agglutinated foraminifera live in benthic environments meaning that they live predominantly at the sediment-water interface. Agglutinated species are commonly found in coastal estuaries and marshes and below the carbonate compensation depth (CCD).

Chamber Arrangement

Aperture Placement

Aperture Form

Foram Species: *Miliammina fusca* (Brady, 1870)

How to ID?

- Tests agglutinated, composed of detrital grains in an organic cement.
 - White to pale brown in color
- Tests elongate and ovate.
- Chambers coiled in a milioline arrangement.
- Aperture terminal with a tooth.
 - May be produced on a short neck

Commonly confused species:

- *Miliammina petila*

Foram Species: *Balticamina pseudomacrescens*
(Bronnimann, Lutze and Whittaker, 1989)

How to ID?

- Tests agglutinated abundant organic cement.
- Trochospirally coiled.
 - Deep stairstep umbilicus
- Has two apertures.
 - primary interiomarginal slit aperture, sometimes with apertural lip
 - secondary umbilical aperture.

Commonly confused species:

- *Entzia macrescens*
- *Trochammina inflata*

Foram Species: *Haplophragmoides* spp. (Cushman, 1910)

How to ID?

- Tests agglutinated pale brown in color and tends to have a smoother finish.
- Plainispirally coiled.
- Interiomarginal aperture.

Commonly confused species:

- *Haplophragmoides maniliaensis* and *H. wilberti* (Andersen, 1953) are difficult to differentiate so are grouped as *Haplophragmoides* spp. in several studies.
- *H. maniliaensis* is more lobate (images below) than *H. wilberti*

Foram Species: *Entzia macrescens* (Brady, 1870)

Formerly *Jadammina macrescens*

How to ID?

- Tests agglutinated.
- Very low trochospiral coil.
 - compressed with a shallow umbilicus.
- Interiomarginal primary slit aperture
 - one or more large areal pores on the face of the last chamber.

Commonly confused species:

- *Trochammina inflata*
- *Balticammina pseudomacrescens*

Foram Species: *Trochammina inflata* (Montagu, 1808)

How to ID?

- Tests agglutinated, often smoothly finished surface.
- Trochospirally coiled with globular chambers.
 - Chambers increasing gradually in size as added.
 - Earlier chambers completely covered by later chambers
- Aperture interiomarginal slit with a lip.

Commonly confused species:

- *Trochammina inflata* and *Entzia macrescens*

Foram Species: *Bullopora irregularis* (d'Orbigny, 1850)

Formerly *Trochamminita* spp. *irregularis*

How to ID?

- Test agglutinated
- Plainispirally enrolled at least in the early stage
 - later chambers irregular in form and arrangement
- Sutures radial in early part, slightly depressed
- Aperture areal
 - One or more rounded to irregular openings in the lower part of the apertural face
 - Each surrounded by a distinct lip.

Commonly confused species:

none

Foram Species: *Tiphotrocha comprimata* (Cushman & Brönnimann, 1948)

How to ID?

- Test agglutinated
- Trochospiral, flattened or more commonly lenticular, chambers increasing rapidly in size as added
- Sutures strongly oblique on spiral side and may be depressed
- Only four to five outer chambers visible on the umbilical side
 - The final one occupying much of the umbilical surface and appearing T-shaped because of its pronounced umbilical lobe
- Aperture at the end of the umbilical chamber lobe
 - Directed either into the umbilicus or backward toward the earlier chambers
 - May be partially covered by a shelflike lip.

Commonly confused species:
none

Foram Species: *Arenoperrella mexicana* (Kornfeld, 1931)

How to ID?

- Test agglutinated
- Low trochospiral coil
- Chambers increasing gradually in size,
- Sutures radial
- Primary aperture a straight to curved slit beginning at or near the base of the apertural face
 - Slightly to the spiral side of the equatorial position and directed upward at an angle to the plane of coiling,
 - Aperture surrounded by a thin and delectate lip that may extend across the base so that the aperture becomes areal rather than interiomarginal
- Supplementary openings present at the apex of the final chamber.

Commonly confused species:

- *Entzia macrescens*

Foraminifera Elevation Ranges

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All illustrations in Foram section drawn by Mira Anderberg

Diatoms in Earthquake Reconstructions

What is a diatom?

Diatoms are a type of single-celled algae that live in aquatic environments. They produce hard outer shells called frustules made of silica (a glass-like material). These frustules preserve well in sediment and can remain intact for thousands of years. Each species of diatom has a unique shape and pattern, which allows scientists to identify them and learn about the past environment in which they lived.

Why do we study diatoms?

Studying diatoms has many applications in paleoecology and environmental reconstruction. Particular species of diatoms are sensitive to factors such as salinity, nutrient levels, temperature, and tidal inundation. Even within estuaries and marshes, different species are most abundant in specific zones. By studying the assemblages of diatoms preserved in sediment cores, we can infer the elevation at which they lived and reconstruct past environments, including changes caused by earthquakes or tsunamis.

Where do they live?

Diatoms inhabit nearly all aquatic environments from freshwater to marine. Freshwater diatoms are found in lakes, streams, and the highest parts of marshes. Brackish species live in tidally influenced estuaries and marshes where salinity levels vary. Marine diatoms are found in coastal waters and seafloor sediments, where they tolerate and prefer higher salinity conditions.

Anatomy of a pennate diatom

Anatomy of a centric diatom

What do you need to study diatoms?

- Glass beakers
- Hot plate
- Deionized water (DI water)
- 30% hydrogen peroxide
- Falcon tubes
- Centrifuge
- Pipets
- Glass slides and slide covers
- Heat activate glue
- Light microscope

How to sample diatoms:

Digest the Organic Material

After subsampling, add hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) to your samples to remove organic matter.

- At room temperature, digestion can take up to 4 weeks.
- If using a hot plate, the process takes about 4 hours.

Clean the Samples

After digestion, add deionized (DI) water to your samples and centrifuge them to remove H₂O₂.

- Centrifuge the samples at least 3 times to remove the hydrogen peroxide.
- After each spin, carefully pour off the liquid, without losing sample, and refill the tube with fresh DI water.

Prepare the Cover Slips

Add your cleaned sample to cover slips

- Place clean glass cover slips on a flat surface and add drops of DI water to each cover slip.
- Pipette a small amount (aliquot) of your cleaned sample onto each cover slip.
- Let the cover slips dry on a clean surface for about 24 hours.

Mount the Slides

The next day, use a heat reactive adhesive to glue the cover slips to the glass slides

- Add a small amount of heat-reactive glue (like Naphrax) to a clean glass slide.
- Gently place the dried cover slip (sample side down) onto the glue.
- Put the slide on a hot plate and heat until the glue finishes reacting (bubbling stops).
- Remove the slide from the heat and set it aside to cool.

Definitions

Apex- Each end of an elongate (pennate)

Areola- Pore-like opening in the valve wall, usually round or slightly elongate (plural: areolae)

Central Area- A space at the center of a diatom valve, can be a diagnostic feature

Centric- Refers to valves that are circular or disc-shaped

Frustule- The ornamented, silica casing surrounding a diatom cell, made of two attached halves (valves)

Pennate- Diatoms with elongate forms, many types with raphe systems

Raphe- An elongate opening or slit in the wall of a benthic diatom that allows cell material to extrude. Usually in the center or at one margin of a valve

Striae- Rows of pores or areolae on a diatom valve

Valve- One half of a diatom frustule, two connecting valves encase the diatom cell material

Pre-1700 CE Earthquake Diatoms (marsh soil)

Diatoms from core MD1403B: 116 cm (McDaniel Slough marsh, Humboldt Bay, 1700 CE marsh soil)

References: 3-6

Pre-1700 CE Earthquake Diatoms (marsh soil)

Observed elevations for diatoms from core MD1403B: 116 cm (McDaniel Slough marsh, Humboldt Bay, 1700 CE marsh soil)

Post-1700 CE Earthquake Diatoms (tidal mud)

Diatoms from core MD1403B: 114 cm (McDaniel Slough marsh, Humboldt Bay, mud above 1700 CE contact)

Caloneis westii

Campylodiscus neofastuosa

Cocconeis scutellum
(araphid valve)

Metascaloneis tumida

Navicula digitoradiata

Gyrosigma centropunctatum

Diploneis bombus

Mastogloia exigua
(focus on exterior)

Mastogloia exigua
(focus on interior)

Gyrosigma wansbeckii

Gyrosigma californica

Scale bar = 10 μ m

Post-1700 CE Earthquake Diatoms (tidal mud)

Observed elevations for diatoms from core MD1403B: 114 cm (McDaniel Slough marsh, Humboldt Bay, mud above 1700 CE contact)

Metascolioneis tumida

Caloneis westii

Navicula digitoradiata

Gyrosigma wansbeckii

Gyrosigma californica

Campylodiscus neofastuosus

Diploneis bombus

Scale bar = 10 μ m

Post-1700 CE Earthquake Diatoms (tidal mud)

Diatoms from core MD1403B: 114 cm (McDaniel Slough marsh, Humboldt Bay, mud above 1700 CE contact)

EXTRA OBSERVATIONS

Post-1700 CE Earthquake Diatoms (tidal mud)

Observed elevations for diatoms from core MD1403B: 114 cm (McDaniel Slough marsh, Humboldt Bay, mud above 1700 CE contact)

Scale bar = 10 μ m

Diatom Identification Tips

Tips for identifying different taxa at Humboldt Bay

Gyrosigma wansbeckii
Raphe is sigmoid and the central area is small and round

Gyrosigma californica
Valve is large, raphe is sigmoid and the central area is large and irregularly shaped

Nitzschia CSZ015
Valve sigmoid and tapers from about halfway between the center and end; striae are distinctive and stand out

Nitzschia sigma
Valve sigmoid and very straight on one side; striae very fine and delicate

Metascioneis tumida
Large valve, striae distinctly punctate, raphe is diagonal from end to end

Navicula kefvingsensis
Large valve, thick distinctive thick striae, and squarish central area

Diploneis smithii
Thick radiate striae made of two rows of areolae (pores)

Diploneis decipiens var. parallela
Simple parallel striae and single row of pores along each side of the raphe

Scale bar = 10 μ m

Diploneis interrupta
Strongly radiate striae, discontinuous at the middle of the valve

Diploneis stroemi
Parallel to gently radiate striae, continuous at the middle of the valve

Diploneis bombus
Large, distinctive areolae, only a few per row

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